

A STUDY ON AN ALUMINIUM ALLOY PROCESSED THROUGH SEVERE PLASTIC DEFORMATION

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Abstract: Equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) is one of the severe plastic deformation (SPD) techniques used to develop ultrafine-grained (UFG) materials. In this technique, large amount of shear strain is introduced in the material, without any change in the cross-sectional dimensions. Al alloy are promising light weight high strength materials, wherein precipitation strengthening will be possible. In this investigation ECAP is used to enhance the strength in the Al alloy. ECAP processing was carried out in a die having an internal angle between two channels (Φ) of 120° and outer arc curvature (Ψ) of 30° . Optical microscopy was used to study the microstructures before and after ECAP processing. To assess the mechanical properties, microhardness measurement and tensile tests were conducted. In homogenized condition, large grains of size of $160\ \mu\text{m}$ were observed. After ECAP processing, significant grain refinement was observed the grain size of the alloy was decreased to $1\ \mu\text{m}$. Microhardness and strength of the alloy was increased ECAP processing. In homogenized condition, microhardness of the alloy is 90 Hv. After ECAP processing, the microhardness of the alloy is increased to 175 Hv. In homogenized condition, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 115 MPa. After ECAP processing, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 200 MPa.

Keywords: SPD, ECAP, Al alloy, Grain refinement

1. INTRODUCTION

Grain size of a material plays a very significant role in the mechanical properties. According to Hall-Petch equation, the strength of the material increases with decrease in the grain size [1]. This leads to an increase in the interest in developing materials with extremely small grain sizes. Due to several benefits, interest is towards the development of new techniques to produce ultrafine-grained (UFG) materials (grain size $< 1\ \mu\text{m}$). Since, conventional processing techniques possess limitations in decreasing the grain size of the materials to the order of a few micrometers, UFG is accomplished either by bottom-up approach or top-down approach [2].

In the bottom-up approach, individual atoms or molecules are consolidated into bulk material, like in inert gas consolidation, electro-deposition, hot isostatic pressing, etc. Whereas, in top-down approach, solid materials, usually having coarse grain (CG) structure are refined into fine grain structures [2]. Top-down approach could be accomplished by conventional processing and severe plastic deformation (SPD) techniques. Conventional processing techniques, like cold rolling results in grain refinement. However, structures formed from conventional processing techniques are usually having low angle grain boundaries. SPD techniques result in high degree of grain refinement along with the formation of high angle grain boundaries. It also leads to the accumulation of high plastic strain in the material [3]. The presence of a high fraction of high angle grain boundaries is very important to achieve significant improvement in the mechanical properties [2].

SPD is a metal forming technique in which very high plastic strain is imposed on the material without any significant change in the overall dimensions. Numerous techniques are established for SPD processing of materials. These include High pressure torsion (HPT) [4], Equal channel angular extrusion or pressing (ECAE or ECAP) [5], Cyclic extrusion and compression (CEC) [6], Accumulative roll bonding (ARB) [7], Repetitive corrugation and straightening (RCS) [8], Constrained groove pressing (CGP) [9] and Multi-directional forging (MDF) [10]. Among these techniques, the ECAP technique is very effective because of its simplicity. The strain space is virtually unlimited in ECAP processing, but other conventional

techniques generally require a shape change or dimension reduction during processing for achieving large values of plastic strain. So, the ECAP processed materials exhibit high dislocation densities which lead to much higher hardness and strength than the materials processed by other conventional techniques. Also, ECAP processing results in high degree of grain refinement along with the formation of high angle grain boundaries.

Even though the strength of the material can be improved by various techniques like heat treatment, adding alloying and rare-earth elements, and coating techniques, these processes have various limitations. For instance, not all properties of all materials will be improved in heat treatment process, or adding alloying and rare-earth elements into the material changes composition and phases of the alloy system, also only surface properties could be improved in coating techniques. Compared to these techniques strengthening via grain refinement through SPD techniques is more attractive because of several benefits, like simplicity in operation, cost effectiveness, and development of homogenous structure and properties throughout the material.

Aluminium and its alloys are considered as the reliable materials in the field of engineering applications. The Al-Zn-Mg alloys are identified as the strongest and hardest alloys among the aluminium alloy families [11]. The Al-Zn-Mg alloys possess high strength and toughness characteristics. The Al-Zn-Mg alloys have a wide acceptance in the fabrication of engineering equipments where high strength to weight ratio is an important criterion. The important applications of these alloys are in aerospace, military equipments and light weight structures [12]. Al-Zn-Mg alloys possess good tensile properties, dimensional stability, machinability and are recommended for service at elevated temperatures. The strengthening of the Al-Zn-Mg could be enhanced by various SPD techniques [13].

Nanostructured materials produced by severe plastic deformation are 100% dense, contamination-free, and sufficiently large for use in real commercial structural applications. These materials are found to have high strength, good ductility, superior superplasticity, a low friction coefficient, high wear resistance, enhanced high cycle fatigue life, and good corrosion resistance.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

In recent years, interest in the production of UFG materials through SPD techniques has attracted the interest of many researchers. Grain size having 0.1 to 1 μm comes under UFG microstructure category [2]. Conventional metal forming processes result in changes in the dimension of the worked material and it limits the amount of strain that can be produced in the material. Hence, there exists a lower limit of grain size that can be achieved by these processes [3]. Also, the strain produced is often inhomogeneous in these processes. SPD techniques do not change the dimensions of the material. Thus, the limitation due to dimensional change for producing large strains is avoided. Compared to conventional metal forming processes the mechanical properties obtained by SPD techniques are homogenous and can be superior [14].

Severe plastic deformation (SPD) refers to the experimental procedures of metal forming operations that are used to impose very high strains on the materials leading to exceptional grain refinement. A unique feature of SPD processing is that high strain is imposed without any significant change in the overall dimensions of the work piece [15]. The materials processed by SPD will have high angle grain boundaries generated due to very large strain under high pressure at relatively low temperature and without much significant change in overall dimensions of the product. SPD techniques have several advantages compared to other bottom-up

approach techniques [2]. SPD techniques result in overcoming several difficulties connected with porosity, in compacted samples and impurities from consolidation of ball milled materials. Development of bulk nanostructured materials using SPD techniques is an alternative to the existing techniques of nano powder compacting. Among various SPD techniques, ECAP is attractive for various reasons, like simplicity in operation, adaptable to large samples and homogeneity in the processed materials [2].

Segal and co-workers were the first to develop the equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) in 1972. This process has now become the most widely used experimental technique compared to other SPD techniques. ECAP is an innovative process of severe plastic deformation capable of producing large plastic strain in polycrystalline materials. The terms ECAP and ECAE (equal channel angular extrusion) are used interchangeably in the scientific literature. However, in this process, there is no reduction in the cross-sectional area of the billets, so the term ECAP is generally adopted [15].

In the ECAP process, the deformation takes place by pure shear. The setup consists of a die having channels of equal cross-section which intersect at an angle. A sample of uniform cross-section (may be of circular or square cross-section) is pressed through these channels. Large amount of shear strain are induced in the sample as it passes the plane of intersection of the two channels which in turn causes significant reduction in the grain size. The significant feature of ECAP is that the dimension of the sample is unchanged during deformation; therefore, the same material could be processed repetitively to induce very high strains and to produce UFG structure.

To develop an optimum microstructure with uniform and equiaxed grains separated by high-angle grain boundaries, these conditions should be fulfilled. (i) Development of slip traces over large angular ranges on each of the three orthogonal planes. (ii) A regular and periodic restoration of the equiaxed structure during each consecutive passes. (iii) The occurrence of deformation on all three orthogonal planes. This criterion is fulfilled in using route B_C in 90° die. While in 120° die, the effectiveness of route B_C is less compared to route A. Even though, the route B_C is considered as the optimum procedure. The channel angle, Φ , is very important experimental factor as it decides the strain introduced in each pass.

Large amount of ultrafine equiaxed grains and grain structure with high fraction of high angle grain boundaries is achieved easily, when the sample is subjected to a very intense plastic strain using a die with a channel angle of 90°. When the die angle is increased, the grain structure will have high fraction of low angle grain boundaries. It should be noted that, experimentally it is easier to press samples in dies having an angle larger than 90°, particularly for hard materials and materials with low ductility. The important factor is that the microstructure developed is independent of total cumulative strain and suggested to ensure a very high strain rate on each separate pass to induce high fraction of high angle grain boundaries and to produce more refined grains. It is possible to produce excellent microstructures using a die with $\Phi = 60^\circ$ and the average grain size produced will be slightly smaller than with the die having $\Phi = 90^\circ$.

The angle of curvature, ψ , denotes the outer arc where the two parts of the channel intersect within the die. This angle plays only a minor role in determining the strain imposed on the sample and has relatively less effect on the strain imposed on the sample when the angle Φ is more than 90°. However, it is important to understand the influence of this angle in the production of UFG materials. The sample no longer remains in contact with the die walls at the outer corner because of the development of the corner gap or dead zone which is formed at the outer corner when the sample

pass through the die. The angle subtended by the corner gap depends upon the rate of strain hardening in the material. It is also possible to introduce a corner angle on the inner surface where the two parts of the channel intersect, but it is not recommendable because of practical difficulties. It is reasonable to construct a die with an outer angle of curvature of $\psi = 20^\circ$ to 30° to achieve optimum processing conditions.

Pressing speed is one of the variable parameters in the ECAP process. The reported data demonstrates that the pressing speed has no significant influence on the equilibrium size of the ultrafine grains formed by ECAP, but recovery occurs more easily when pressing is done at lower speeds. Processing at lower speeds develops more equilibrated microstructures. Also, there is an abrupt heating of the samples when processed with a higher speed.

The processing temperature plays an important role in ECAP process by directly affecting grain size achieved in ECAP. Various studies have been conducted to understand the effect of processing temperature on ECAP process. Fraction of low-angle grain boundaries increases with increasing processing temperature, due to the faster rate of recovery which lead to increase in the annihilation of dislocations within the grains and a consequent decrease in the quantity of dislocations developed in the sub-grains. Optimum UFG microstructures will be attained when the processing is performed at the lowest possible temperature, where the processing could be performed without the introduction of any significant cracking in the samples. Higher strengths are obtained if processing is carried out at lower temperatures and as the processing temperature is increased the strength decreases. By maintaining low processing temperature, both the smallest possible grain size and the highest fraction of high-angle boundaries could be achieved.

Smaller grain size and high dislocation densities formed in the materials processed by ECAP lead to much higher strength and hardness compared to the coarse-grained materials. But, ECAP processed materials generally possess low ductility. Compared to conventional metal forming process, decrease in ductility in the ECAP processed samples is comparatively less. Literatures stating increase in both the strength and the ductility of the material after ECAP processing are also available. Simultaneous increase in both the strength and the ductility was observed in copper processed upto sixteen passes. It has been suggested that, it is attributed to the increase in the fraction of high angle grain boundaries with increase in strain. Also, consequent change in the deformation mechanisms due to ECAP is attributed to increase in the tendency towards the occurrence of grain boundary sliding and grain rotation. Introduction of ageing treatment after ECAP has a noticeable effect on the strength and the ductility of the material. It could be concluded that, grain refinement through ECAP leads to development of an exclusive combination of the strength and the ductility.

3. METHODOLOGY

The ECAP die was fabricated in split type design and align pins were provided for proper alignment. The ECAP die was machined with two channels of 16 mm diameter intersecting at an internal angle (Φ) of 120° and outer arc of curvature (Ψ) of 30° . The equivalent strain imposed on the sample with these angular values in each pass is 0.667. The ECAP die and the punch were machined from H11 tool steel and heat treated to attain 50 HRC hardness. Holes are provided in the ECAP die for placing heating coils to heat the die to the required processing temperature. Figure 3.4 shows the dimensions of the ECAP die in mm. In the present work, ECAP processing was carried out in a 40-ton universal testing machine (UTM). For ECAP processing the die blocks were held together and aligned with the help of align pins.

Die blocks were then clamped with the help of three pair of flat clamps bolted with adequate pressure. In the present work, route B_C was adopted. It results in uniform distribution of the strain in the material compared to other routes. Also, route B_C provides optimum processing condition for attaining a homogeneous microstructure of equiaxed grains separated by high angle grain boundaries and hence isotropic mechanical properties are expected. Also, processing through route B_C gives shearing over larger angular ranges by comparison with other processing routes. The ECAP process was carried out by pressing the sample at a constant speed of 0.5 mm/s. To reduce the friction between the die and the sample molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2) was used as the lubricant. Prior to each pass, the die was heated upto the processing temperature and then the sample was inserted in to the die and kept for 15 min so that the equilibrium temperature was established in the sample and the die. While processing, the whole die setup was maintained at the processing temperature using an inbuilt heater. After processing, the sample is manually removed from the die. Homogenization of the procured material was carried at 480 °C upto 20 hours. For ECAP processing, homogenized material was machined to a diameter of 15.9 mm and a length of 85 mm parallel to the ingot axis.

Carl-Zeiss Optical microscopy software was used to observe the microstructure of the material before and after ECAP processing. To access the mechanical properties of the alloy mechanical tests like microhardness measurement and tensile test were conducted on the unprocessed and the processed samples. Microhardness of the samples was measured by using Vickers microhardness tester, The values of the Vickers microhardness, H_v , were determined by imposing a load of 50 gm for 15 sec according to ASTM E384 standard. On each sample, 12 hardness measurements were carried out and the average value of microhardness was calculated by eliminating the highest and lowest values and averaging the remaining 10 measurements. To evaluate the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the elongation to failure (ductility) of the unprocessed and processed samples, tensile tests were conducted at room temperature and at a constant cross head speed of 0.1 mm/min by using universal testing equipment. For tensile testing, unprocessed and processed samples were machined to tensile test samples as per the ASTM E8 standard. ECAP processed samples were machined parallel to the processing direction. In each condition, three samples were tested to confirm the repeatability of the results and average values were considered.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The literature on the ECAP processing indicates that the optimum mechanical properties could be achieved by processing the material at lowest possible temperature. In this regard, material was attempted to process at minimum possible temperature. Only at 200 °C, material was successfully processed upto four passes in route B_C , without failure. After four passes, processing was stopped, since in route B_C deformation restores the equiaxed microstructure in all three planes after every four successive passes.

In homogenized condition, due to the recrystallization effect uniform size grains were observed. In the homogenized condition, grains in the size of 160 μm were observed. It is noticed that, ECAP processing leads to significant grain refinement in the alloy. In this condition, grain structure was refined by the introduction of the sub-grains. Due to the formation of new sub-grains, more refined grain structure was observed. Large volume of shear bands was observed. The shear bands direction is nearly parallel to the processing direction. The size of the shear bands measured at this stage is 1 μm . Homogeneous and equiaxed microstructure was observed after fourth passes. In the present work, route B_C was employed. It may be noted that, in

route B_C deformation restores the equiaxed structure in each plane after every four consecutive passes and deformation will take place in all three planes. Also, processing in route B_C gives shearing over larger angular ranges by comparison with other processing routes. In homogenized condition, microhardness of the alloy is 90 Hv. After ECAP processing, the microhardness of the alloy is increased to 175 Hv. After ECAP processing, significant increase in the microhardness was observed.

In homogenized condition, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 115 MPa. After ECAP processing, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 200 MPa. After ECAP processing, significant increase in the ultimate tensile strength was observed. The increase in the microhardness and ultimate tensile strength of the alloy after ECAP processing is attributed to significant decrease in the grain size and different strengthening mechanisms. They are (i) grain refinement strengthening (ii) strain or work hardening effect and (iii) precipitation strengthening.

Materials prepared by SPD processing usually have high dislocation densities, non-equilibrium grain boundaries, and other structural features associated with intense plastic straining. The small grain sizes and high defect densities give these materials a much higher strength than their coarse-grained counterparts. On the other hand, these structural features may also lead to reduce ductility. Materials having high strength usually exhibit low ductility is irrespective of whether their strength is achieved through compositional differences, thermo-mechanical processing, phase transformations, or other methods. In general, it is reasonable to anticipate that materials processed by SPD will follow the same trend. It is important to note that SPD processing reduces the ductility to a smaller extent than more conventional deformation processing techniques such as rolling, drawing, and extrusion.

Equal-channel angular pressing is implemented by repeatedly pressing an ingot through a special die with two channels of equal cross section, intersecting at an angle of 120° . Each pass through the die imparts an additional effective strain of approximately 0.667. In the case of hard-to-deform materials, the deformation is imposed at elevated temperatures. Elevated temperature processing has some requirements with respect to heat resistance and durability of the die. Significant microstructure refinement can be obtained quite easily both in pure metals and in alloys by ECAP. However, producing homogeneous UFG nanostructures with high-angle grain boundaries by ECAP requires particular attention to equal channel angular processing parameters.

Homogeneous UFG microstructure can be obtained in alloys after four to six passes, following route B_C . During this process, the billet is turned between consecutive passes in one direction around its axis by an angle of 90° . The analysis of the shearing characteristics for different processing routes indicates that route B_C leads to reconstruction of the shape of an initially cubic element in the unpressed sample after 4 passes through the die and it leads to a homogeneous equiaxed structure. Modelling of the mechanics of ECAP has shown that contact stresses in the die are of utmost importance in developing SPD processing. Investigations of the influence of the friction between the deforming billet and the die walls have shown that the shear plastic strain during ECAP can be non-uniform along the deformed sample. Through a combination of experimentation and finite-element modelling (FEM), microstructure uniformity can be enhanced and the friction conditions can be optimized.

The basic principle of SPD processing is that a material is subjected to a very large strain but this strain is attained without any concomitant change in the overall dimensions of the sample. Thus, SPD processing differs in a very significant way from more conventional processing techniques such as extrusion, rolling and drawing where the introduction of strain is associated with a reduction in the cross-

sectional area of the work-piece. ECAP uses reasonably large billets and the process may be scaled-up to produce bulk samples suitable for use in industrial applications. Processing by ECAP imposes a very high strain on the sample and thus a very large number of dislocations are introduced into the material. After a single pass the microstructure consists of bands of elongated sub-grains with the boundaries having low angles of misorientation, but with subsequent passes the microstructure evolves gradually into an array of ultrafine and essentially equiaxed grains separated by high-angle grain boundaries.

Microstructure introduced in ECAP gradually evolves towards a relatively homogeneous array of equiaxed grains separated by high-angle grain boundaries. A banded sub-grain structure is clearly visible after 1 pass, where these bands are closely aligned with the shear direction, but this microstructure evolves rapidly so that there is an array of essentially equiaxed grains after 4 passes. The shearing direction is no longer evident. The evolution in microstructure is evident also in the gradual increase in the fraction of high angle boundaries. It is apparent from the observations that processing by ECAP provides two significant opportunities in the fabrication of materials with unusual properties. First, there is the well-established demonstration that ECAP leads to arrays of ultrafine grains that are typically in the sub-micrometer range. These sizes are much smaller than those achieved through conventional thermomechanical processing. Second, there is clear evidence for an evolution in the grain boundary character distributions from predominantly low-angle boundaries in the initial stages of ECAP to reasonably high fractions of high-angle boundaries after large numbers of passes and consequently after the imposition of fairly high strains. Low-angle boundaries exhibit little or no grain boundary sliding, the occurrence of superplasticity requires the presence of a reasonably high fraction of high-angle boundaries.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, Al alloy was processed by ECAP in a die having an internal angle between two channels (Φ) of 120° . The processing was carried out in route B_C. Microstructural study was and mechanical properties were assessed before and after ECAP processing. Al alloy was successfully processed at 200 °C upto four passes. In homogenized condition, large grains of size of 160 μm were observed. After ECAP processing, significant grain refinement was observed the grain size of the alloy was decreased to 1 μm . Microhardness and strength of the alloy was increased ECAP processing. In homogenized condition, microhardness of the alloy is 90 Hv. After ECAP processing, the microhardness of the alloy is increased to 175 Hv. In homogenized condition, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 115 MPa. After ECAP processing, ultimate tensile strength of the alloy is 200 MPa.

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